

Correlations between Google Search Volumes of COVID-19 symptoms and infections in Germany over the course of the pandemic

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ABSTRACT

Correlations between the search volume of COVID-19 symptoms and case numbers were found in some countries during the first phase of the pandemic. The objective of this study is to find out whether such correlations also occur in Germany, and whether they also emerge in the further course of the pandemic. In this study, data from Google trends with 19 different COVID-19 symptoms as search terms were examined with corona infection figures from the Robert Koch Institute for the four half-years in 2020 and 2021. It was found that the search volume for e.g. cough, aching limbs or sore throat correlate strongly with the covid case numbers over the pandemic period to date. In addition, it was found that more symptoms correlate at the beginning of the pandemic than later in its course.

KEYWORDS

Coronavirus, COVID-19, Search Terms, Germany, Google, Google Trends, COVID-19 Symptoms, COVID-19 Cases, TLCC

1 INTRODUCTION

Even almost two Years after the initial outbreak of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), the daily number of infected persons keeps fluctuating, ranging between 280,000 and 900,000 cases worldwide from January 1, 2021 to December 15, 2021 [14]. This occurrence of further epidemic waves shows, that a widely spread surveillance is still necessary to implement protective measures like social distancing [9]. The most common metrics to track COVID-19, such as confirmed cases, hospitalization rates, and deaths, have the disadvantage of reporting delays. The availability of a reliable timely indicator of emerging COVID-19 outbreaks would help to promptly enable effective public health action. Besides other data sources like Twitter or Google Trends turned out to be a possible indicator for the early identification of COVID-19 outbreaks[10]. Previously, it was found that there were other correlations between google search volumes and other medical occurrences, such as the influenza [8] or MERS [18].

Some research has already addressed correlations between COVID-19 indicators (deaths, confirmed cases) and the search volume of various keywords in google trends. Most of these papers focus on the early stage of the pandemic. Moreover, they either focus on individual countries, e.g. USA [19] [15] [1] [13], Spain [7], Italy [2], Taiwan [6], China [11], or compare occurrences in several countries [12] [4] [3]. There is no work available at the moment that refers only to Germany. This study aims to fill this research gap by determining whether correlations between disease-related symptoms as

search terms and COVID-19 cases in Germany still can be identified. Also it aims to find out whether correlations of specific keywords and case numbers have changed over time.

2 LITERATURE

Various Research attempts already addressed the question if Search Keyword volumes on Google might correlate with other measurable COVID-19 metrics, using data from Google Trends. The articles found covered different time periods between the end of December 2019 and the end of May 2020, ranging in length from 3 weeks to almost 4 months. A summary of the individual time periods can be found in table 1. The table also contains information on the COVID-19 reference metrics used in each case, with each of which the search volume in Google Trends was compared. In most publications, the daily COVID-19 case counts and deaths were used as a metric. Peköz et al [15] compare search trends with hospitalisation figures, and Jimenez et al [7] investigate correlations with case, death, hospitalisation and intensive care patient figures.

Table 1: COVID-19 metric and Google Trends Data Timespan by Publication

Publication	Reference metric	GT Timespan ^a
Ahmad et al [1]	Cases	Jan - Apr
Brunori and Resce [2]	Deaths	24 Feb - 06 Apr
Effenberger et al [3]	Cases, Deaths	31 Dec 19 - 01 Apr
Higgins et al [4]	Cases, Deaths	09 Jan - 06 Apr
Husnayain et al [6]	Cases	05 Dec 19 - 08 Feb
Jimenez et al [7]	Cases (PCR), Hospitalizations, ICU, Deaths	20 Feb - 20 May
Li et al [11]	Cases	16 Jan - 11 Feb
Lu and Reis [12]	Cases, Deaths	01 Jan - 20 Apr
Mavragani et al [13]	Cases, Deaths	04 Mar - 15 Apr
Peköz et al [15]	Hospitalizations	01 Jan - 14 Apr
Yuan et al [19]	Cases, Deaths	01 Mar - 07 Apr

^aIf not stated otherwise, all Dates in Year 2020.

Table 2 lists various search terms used in the individual studies. It notably shows that some studies refer to the search resonance of

the disease itself [3] [6] [11] [13], while others examine the search volume of disease-typical symptoms [1] [2] [4] [7] [12] [15] [19]. Ahmad et al [1] specifically address gastrointestinal symptoms of the Coronavirus. Lu and Reis [12] point out that the use of general keywords related to the disease itself (e.g. 'coronavirus') has a higher variability in correlation with reported cases of disease or death, as these search terms are thought to be used by people seeking general information about the disease, but do not necessarily have symptoms themselves.

Furthermore, there is discussion about a possible accumulation of search terms due to an increase in media presentation. According to Brunori and Resce [2], this applies not only to search queries about the disease itself, but also to the search for symptoms, as the person searching may obtain information about possible symptoms after learning about them in the media, without them actually occurring.

Table 2: Search terms used by Publication

Publication	Search Keywords
Ahmad et al [1]	Aguesia, Abdominal pain, loss of appetite, anorexia, diarrhea, vomiting
Brunori and Resce [2]	Cough, Dry Cough, Fever, Sore throat, Seasonal Flu, Lost of Taste, Lost of Smell
Effenberger et al [3]	Coronavirus (Virus)
Higgins et al [4]	Coronavirus, COVID-19, Fever, Shortness of Breath, Cough, Sputum, Anosmia, Ageusia, Nasal congestion, Rhinorrhea, Sneezing, Sore throat, Headache, Myalgia, Chest pain, Eye pain, Diarrhea
Husnayain et al [6]	Corona, Coronavirus, handwashing, face masks, surgical masks
Jimenez et al [7]	Fatigue, coronavirus, COVID 19, covid 19, COVID19, diarrhea, sore throat, fever, pneumonia, lost sense of smell, cough
Li et al [11]	coronavirus, pneumonia
Lu and Reis [12]	Coronavirus symptoms, Coronavirus test, Fever, Cough, Coronavirus, Runny nose, Dry cough, Sore throat, Chills, Shortness of Breath
Mavragani et al [13]	coronavirus (virus)
Peköz et al [15]	Fever, Cough, Sore throat, Dry cough, Shortness of breath
Yuan et al [19]	COVID heart, COVID pneumonia, COVID, Cough, Coronavirus, Pneumonia, COVID diabetes, SARS-CoV2, High temperature

As already mentioned, the papers found examine diverse regions. In addition to publications focusing on individual countries, including the USA [19] [15] [1] [13], Spain [7], Italy [2], Taiwan [6] or China [11], Higgins et al [4] underpin a comparison of countries most affected at the time, such as Italy, Spain, individual states of the USA, as well as an analysis of global search volume. A similar approach is taken by Effenberger et al [3], who compare 12 other countries in addition to the global search volume. Lu and Reis [12] compare 32 countries on six continents.

All of the observed publications were able to identify significant correlations between the search volume in Google Trends and COVID-19 metrics. However, there were differences especially in the lag between the increase in search queries and the increase in the respective COVID-19 metrics. For example, the study by Brunori and Resce [2] found a lag between an increase in search volume and an increase in deaths of 3-10 days, while Lu and Reis [12] found a delay of 22 days and Yuan et al [19] reported a lag of 19 days.

The lag between the peak in search volume and the peak in the number of reported cases is indicated as 8-12 days [11], 11 days [7], 11.5 days [3], 12 days [4], 12-14 days [19], 18.53 days [12] and 28 days [1]. Peköz et al [15] show a gap between an increase in search volume and an increase in hospitalisations of 7-14 days. Mavragani et al [13] and Husnayain et al [6] do not specify the duration of the lag.

Lu and Reis [12] also conclude, that the order of increase in search volume of symptoms is consistent with the pattern of occurrence of COVID-19 symptoms found in clinical studies.

3 OBJECTIVES

The observed publications only cover the early stages of the pandemic. Lu and Reis [12] assume, that the relationships between search interest volume and COVID-19 incidence might change in the course of time, so one objective of this paper is to determine, whether correlations of symptom related search terms and case incidence have varied since the outbreak of the disease. Also, there is no work known to the author which completely focuses on Germany and the German language, which builds the framework of this research.

4 METHODOLOGY

The data acquisition, preprocessing and calculation of correlations is performed in a Jupyter notebook with python 3.8. The packages pandas, numpy, scipy and matplotlib are used for data handling, mathematical operations and data visualizations, the pytrends package is used to access Google Trends data. The source code can be requested from the author.

COVID-19 case data

The confirmed case data for Germany was extracted from the publicly available COVID-19 dataset from the German Robert-Koch-Institut (RKI). The Dataset was downloaded from ArcGIS [16] on the 3rd of January 2022. The provided dataset contains reportings from german health authorities on a county level. One row contains aggregates to deaths, confirmed and recovered cases for a certain group of people in a certain county per day. The dataset is updated

daily by the RKI starting from the 2nd of January 2020 [16]. The dataset was preprocessed by removing unnecessary columns and aggregating the case data to daily records for whole Germany.

Google Trends data

Google Trends provides data to search term popularity in the Google search from 2004 until present for a given time period. It may be accessed via web interface or API, which was used in this case through the python package pytrends [5]. All requests to the Google API were made with a preconfigured geolocation to Germany, the German language as reference and the Timezone UTC+1. The data was retrieved for four different timeframes with a length of six months each, starting from the 8th of January 2020 until the 31st of December 2021. Each keyword was requested for each Timeframe separately. Google Trends provides values from 0 to 100 representing the relative popularity of a search term. For the chosen timeframe of 6 months a popularity value was returned for each day.

The search terms used base on a collection of 19 possible COVID-19 symptoms from Schilling et al [17], which were used in original german language. The symptoms covered as search terms are: *Husten* (cough), *Fieber* (fever), *Schnupfen* (rhinitis), *Geschmacksverlust* (as loss of taste), *Geruchsverlust* (loss of smell), *Halsschmerzen* (sore throat), *Atemnot* (shortness of breath), *Kopfschmerzen* (headache), *Gliederschmerzen* (aching limbs), *Appetitlosigkeit* (loss of appetite), *Gewichtsverlust* (weight loss), *Übelkeit* (nausea), *Bauchschmerzen* (abdominal pain), *Erbrechen* (vomiting), *Durchfall* (diarrhoea), *Konjunktivitis* (conjunctivitis), *Hautausschlag* (skin rash), *Lymphknotenschwellung* (Lymph node swelling), *Apathie* (apathy), *Somnolenz* (somnolence).

data preparation and analysis

COVID-19 metrics data and Google Trends result were combined into a dataframe for each timeframe containing one observation per day for six months. Since the Google Trends data is normalized to a relative value, the case data also was normalized to a 0 to 100 scale with 100 being the maximum value of one timeframe. Before doing so, the cases series is smoothened by the mean of a surrounding 7-day window to reduce the daily fluctuation of case data. Due to a high fluctuation in the Google Trends results this smoothening method was also applied to the series of all keywords by using a 14-day window.

To calculate the correlation coefficients and determine the lag between a search term volume and the COVID-19 cases, a Time Lagged Cross Correlation (TLCC) method was applied to each timeframe. This method moves each keyword timeseries in a range between -35 and 35 days on the x-axis and calculates the pearson correlation coefficient for each phase. For each combination of relative case volume and relative search volume the highest correlation coefficient and the indicated lag are noted.

For each correlation coefficient value an acceptance threshold of -0.6 or 0.6 was applied to mark all highly correlated terms per timeframe. The results from each timeframe were concatenated to a single dataframe. For each keyword, the sum of relevant correlation occurrences and the standard deviation of the correlation coefficient are calculated across the 4 timeframes, to determine consistency of correlations.

5 RESULTS

The search volume for symptoms of the novel coronavirus increases correlating with the increase in the number of cases, especially in the first half of 2020. In this period, 10 of 19 investigated symptoms show strong positive correlations ($r > 0.6$, or $r < -0.6$). In the second half of 2020, only 7 of 19 symptoms correlate strongly, in the first half of 2021, 8 strong positive correlations can be found, and in the second half of the year, 6 of 19 dependent time series can be identified.

The symptoms *cough* and *aching limbs* exceed the high correlation threshold of $r > 0.6$, or $r < -0.6$ in all four periods. *Sore throat*, *rhinitis*, *loss of taste and smell*, *fever* and *shortness of breath* have a strong positive correlation in three of the six-month periods. Symptoms such as *skin rash*, *nausea*, *weight loss*, etc. do not show strong correlations in any of the four time periods. The complete overview of correlation coefficients can be found in table 3.

The search terms most frequently correlating strongly with case numbers also have relatively low to moderate standard deviations in the correlation coefficient over the four time periods. For example, *cough* has a standard deviation of 0.07, *aching limbs* 0.09, *Sore throat* 0.16, *rhinitis* 0.17, *loss of taste* 0.18, *fever* 0.23 and *loss of smell* 0.26. This indicates that the search terms correlate strongly with the COVID-19 case numbers over the entire pandemic period.

Looking at the lag between the increase in the search volume of a symptom and the increase in the number of COVID-19 infections, we find a value of around 14 days for the most strongly correlated search terms in the first half of 2020. Looking at the second half of 2020, the lags increase significantly to 29-34 days, indicating that the search for the symptoms may be related to other illnesses, as this is the autumn and winter period. This pattern repeats itself again in 2021. The Symptoms *loss of taste* and *loss of smell* show the strongest correlation at a lag between 3 days prior and up to 7 days posterior the COVID-19 peak, which might indicate that these symptoms are searched close to infections being detected.

Figure 1: Google Trends relative search volume for selected keywords and the normalized COVID-19 infections in Germany from 08 Jan 2020 until 31 May 2020

Table 3: Overview of correlation coefficients for COVID-19 cases and keyword per timeframe.

The columns 'r_01_20' represent the correlation coefficient for the first half of 2020, other r_ columns follow an analog scheme. The 'lag_-' columns show the offset time both timeseries are the most correlated with (offset in days). The 'r_std' column show the standard deviation of correlation coefficients per timeframe. The 'relevant' column counts, how many timeframes correlated with $r < -0.6$ or $r > 0.6$.

keyword	r_01_20	lag_01_20	r_02_20	lag_02_20	r_01_21	lag_01_21	r_02_21	lag_02_21	r_std	relevant
cough	0.771578	14.0	0.857787	34.0	0.749112	7.0	0.941333	34.0	0.076031	4
aching limbs	0.728278	11.0	0.914168	29.0	0.808672	5.0	0.663161	-4.0	0.093730	4
sore throat	0.911696	14.0	0.520058	34.0	0.888360	11.0	0.894945	30.0	0.164019	3
rhinitis	0.833087	18.0	0.437495	34.0	0.823972	12.0	0.865269	34.0	0.175298	3
loss of taste	0.953787	-1.0	0.962564	-6.0	0.532948	0.0	0.952859	-1.0	0.183401	3
fever	0.743816	16.0	0.639449	34.0	0.685304	12.0	0.160195	13.0	0.232171	3
loss of smell	0.949971	-2.0	0.958274	-7.0	0.337601	6.0	0.920343	3.0	0.262465	3
shortness of breath	0.965696	4.0	0.385732	-10.0	0.605171	-10.0	-0.135888	-27.0	0.399158	2
headache	0.859077	13.0	0.867532	34.0	0.562815	15.0	-0.309068	-35.0	0.480223	2
conjunctivitis	0.628827	3.0	0.399066	23.0	0.541842	34.0	0.478777	-35.0	0.084257	1
vomiting	0.511141	30.0	0.303290	-23.0	0.684183	-26.0	0.436369	34.0	0.137599	1
solmonence	0.543160	-1.0	0.356824	16.0	0.805886	20.0	0.202739	-26.0	0.224835	1
diarrhoea	0.488988	20.0	-0.619999	-35.0	0.408781	5.0	-0.513037	21.0	0.509897	1
Lymph node swelling	0.356903	-24.0	0.488115	-35.0	0.305610	-30.0	0.167226	-35.0	0.114906	0
apathy	0.407607	27.0	0.087660	-35.0	0.313325	34.0	0.147313	-16.0	0.127733	0
loss of appetite	0.309789	-11.0	0.290448	0.0	0.153778	-35.0	-0.065304	-15.0	0.149717	0
nausea	0.206749	34.0	0.170708	34.0	0.305357	-23.0	-0.390212	-34.0	0.272025	0
weight loss	0.300223	34.0	-0.174786	-35.0	0.538632	-35.0	-0.323951	-31.0	0.348867	0
skin rash	0.534325	7.0	0.023054	-35.0	0.570893	-2.0	-0.275820	-35.0	0.355796	0

Figure 2: Google Trends relative search volume for selected keywords and the normalized COVID-19 infections in Germany from 1 Jun 2020 until 31 Dec 2020

Figure 3: Google Trends relative search volume for selected keywords and the normalized COVID-19 infections in Germany from 1 Jan 2021 until 31 May 2021

Figure 4: Google Trends relative search volume for selected keywords and the normalized COVID-19 infections in Germany from 1 Jun 2021 until 31 Dec 2021

6 DISCUSSION

Comparing the results of this study with the outcomes from the papers reviewed, which also treated COVID-19 symptoms as search terms, it appears that the results are similar in the first phase of the pandemic. For example, Higgins et al [4] found strong correlations between new infections and the search terms for *cough*, *fever*, or *shortness of breath*. These observations are consistent with those from the present study in the first half of 2020. Jimenez et al [7] also found strong positive correlations between new infections and the search terms for *sore throat*, *fever*, *cough*, and *loss of smell*. However, unlike in this case, a strong correlation is also found for the term *diarrhoea*.

Regarding the lag between the increasing addiction trend for symptoms and the increase in new infections, Jimenez et al [7] reported a value of 11 days, Higgins et al [4] 6 days for most symptoms and Lu and Reis [12], for example, 18.34 days for the term *cough*, which is quite compatible with the value of 14 days in this study. It should be noted, that the time period of this study is much longer, at 6 months, compared to up to 4 months in the observed studies.

Given the decrease in the number of search terms correlating with new COVID-19 infections compared to the beginning of the pandemic, the assumption of Lu and Reis [12], that the association of certain search terms with infection numbers will change over the course of the pandemic can be confirmed. However, it can still be seen that some search terms such as *cough*, *aching limbs* or *rhinitis* correlate strongly with case numbers throughout the pandemic period to date, suggesting that these terms may still be able to predict COVID-19 outbreaks [7]. Particular attention is paid to the symptoms of *loss of taste and smell*, which had a very low search volume before the start of the pandemic and have steadily increased in search volume since the beginning of the disease spread. This could mean that these addiction terms are less likely to be associated with other diseases. In this sense, the term *fever* is not particularly suitable for determining the number of new infections,

as the correlation with COVID-19 case numbers has decreased considerably in the course of the pandemic.

Limitations of research

Limitations to this research are found in the use of the only relatively available Google Trends data, as this complicates a comparison of the volume in its total occurrence. The relative presentation could distort actual peaks. Also, the values are constantly adjusted in relation to new search volumes, causing a complication of reproducibility based on later sourced data. Further, factors such as a more present media coverage can lead to an increased search volume of relevant symptoms and thus to a distortion of the correlation values [4]. Also, the changed search volume for a symptom must not necessarily mean that the people searching are affected by a symptom. For example, it may be possible that by the time the pandemic progresses, most of the symptoms are already known and it is no longer necessary to search for them when they occur [12].

7 CONCLUSION

At the beginning of the pandemic, strong correlations with the number of new infections were found for 10 out of 19 search terms, with the search trend for the terms *cough*, *aching limbs*, *sore throat* and *rhinitis* increasing around 14 days before the increase in the number of new infections. In the further waves of the disease, the number of strongly correlated search terms decreased to 6 out of 19, but selected terms remained strongly correlated over the entire course. In conclusion, it appears that Google search trends for symptoms of COVID-19 also correlate with the number of infections in Germany. In addition, correlations for certain symptoms have persisted over the entire term so far.

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